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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the “*Shaping electron wavepackets with light; Shaping light with electron wavepackets*”, the fourth in the planned series of 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars for the Q-SORT project.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars are part of Work Package 3 **Theory, optical testing, and TEM implementation of generalised Sorter** [Months: 1-41], Task 3.5 - Interdisciplinary Training Webinars (M6, M11, M12, M18, M24, M26, M30, M36, M41).

The present document is comprised of 4 Chapters, including Introduction and Conclusions.

The Introduction describes what a webinar is.

Chapter 2 summarises what we mean by Interdisciplinary Training Webinars and what their function is within Q-SORT.

Chapter 3 illustrates context, aims, and content of the fourth interdisciplinary Training Webinar of Q-SORT. The conclusions outline future plans for the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars.

1 INTRODUCTION - WHAT IS A WEBINAR?

A webinar is a web-based seminar which can be streamed either live or on demand. It might be just a simple audio stream, or it might include visual aids, such as PowerPoint slides, recorded video clips, or live software demonstrations.

The experience of a webinar attempts to reproduce the benefits of attending a seminar. Audience members can ask questions and the speaker can survey or poll the audience and get feedback as he or she delivers the information.

Webinar technology providers need to support these interactive elements in addition to the basic delivery of the audio and video streams. Keyboard chat features and Q&A are usually subject to more control, whereby the presenters can see messages from the audience and choose whether to broadcast them to all participants, ignore them, or reply privately.

The Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Webinars make use of Facebook Live as a platform for live streaming. We chose this platform as it provides the best value for money and offers the added advantage of being very widespread. Users are able to pose questions by posting comments below the video. Answers can be provided by specialists during or after the webinar.

2 THE Q-SORT INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINARS

The Q-SORT project is intrinsically interdisciplinary, being born from the cross-fertilisation of three subject areas: light optics (UG, MPI), electron microscopy (CNR, FZJ, UMR, FEI), and biology (MU).

The silo-breaking nature of Q-SORT provides added value through the following cross-fertilisation dynamics: microscopists borrow techniques from light optics specialists and explain back the challenges of the new measurements; biologists explain to physicists the problems that usually arise when studying proteins and suggest alternative proteins for investigation; physicists develop the quantum mechanical approach for cryo-TEM; biologists communicate a priori knowledge to light optics theoreticians in order to streamline efforts in the project work-packages (WP3-WP5).

In order to facilitate mutual learning between physicists and biologists, as well as to foster possible further applications to biology and the life sciences, 9 Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinars have been planned during the lifetime of the project. Their main aim is to function as aids to facilitate the highly interdisciplinary work in WP3 and in the other research WPs. They will do so by providing opportunities for training and mutual learning mentored by senior scientists, for forging a common language, for exchanging ideas for further joint research.

However important their role within Q-SORT, these seminars are meant for everyone, hence the choice to propose them as webinars, so as to reach as wide an audience as possible.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars introduce a sort of 'intermediate level' in the communication of science: i.e. their nature is intermediate between the specialist-to-specialist character of discipline-specific colloquia, talks, and articles and the broad appeal of conventional public understanding of science.

This is why, besides their facilitating function within WP3 and the other research WPs, the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars also play an important role in the dissemination and engagement process. Together with the Website, they ensure that Q-SORT will reach a broad range of pertinent audiences across Europe and beyond.

In the following paragraph we describe the third of the 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars planned for Q-SORT.

3 THE Q-SORT FOURTH INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINAR:

SHAPING ELECTRON WAVEPACKETS WITH LIGHT; SHAPING LIGHT WITH ELECTRON WAVEPACKETS

The “*Shaping electron wavepackets with light; Shaping light with electron wavepackets*” *Interdisciplinary Training Webinar* was recorded and webcast on 29 May 2018, during the first [International Conference on Electron Beam Shaping in Space and Time](#) at [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#). The conference was organised by Q-SORT and the “[Science and Applications of Electron Wavefunctions Shaped and Manipulated by Engineered Nanoholograms](#)” DIP project (*Deutsch-Israelische Projekt cooperation grant*) with the support of [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#) and the [Nanoscience Institute of CNR \(CNR-NANO\)](#).

The webinar featured one of conference invited speakers, **Prof. Ido Kaminer (Technion, Israel Institute of Technology, Israel)**.

For the talk of Ido Kaminer webinar viewers reached 6.6K out of 19295 people reached. Facebook posts related to the webinars held during the Conference reached over 60K people.

The webinar was recorded with one camera, then stored on remote servers for subsequent on-demand viewing.

The content of the Webinar was agreed upon by the Project Coordinator, Dr. Vincenzo Grillo (CNR) with Prof. Ido Kaminer (Technion, Israel Institute of Technology, Israel). and Dr. Luca Marco Carlo Giberti (QED).

The webinar can be re-watched on demand - interested parties can re-play it at their convenience by clicking on the following link:

on the Q-SORT website:

<http://www.qsort.eu/webinar4-shaping-electron-packets-with-light-shaping-light-with-electron-packets/>

on Facebook:

<https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/videos/1282265178573517/>

3.1 TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION

The Q-SORT Fourth Interdisciplinary Training Webinar touches upon the following topics:

- Electron and photon beam shaping
- Electron-light interaction
- Light-electron interaction with shaped beam
- Coherent Bremsstrahlung, Cherenkov and transition radiation
- Plasmon and PINEM (photon-induced near-field electron microscopy)
- Smith-Purcell radiation

The worlds of light microscopy and electron microscopy can ‘talk together’. Recently-developed techniques enable the shaping of wavepackets of photons and electrons: such capabilities could enable new kinds of interactions between light and matter

This talk is geared towards an audience of physicists interested in the unconventional possibilities coming from beam-shaping implementations realised outside the field of electron microscopy.

It also provides an overview of some common misunderstandings and imprecisions in the calculation of electron-light-matter interaction, and available strategies for tackling them in a correct manner.

A lively Q&A session followed after the webinar.

Figure 1 - Screenshot from Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar no. 4

3.2 THE FOURTH INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINAR ON THE Q-SORT WEBSITE

A dedicated webpage for this webinar has been created on the Q-SORT website featuring:

1. the webinar;
2. a short description of the webinar thought for the general public;
3. a short bio of the speaker who offered the talk.

The link to the webpage is:

<http://www.qsort.eu/webinar4-shaping-electron-packets-with-light-shaping-light-with-electron-packets/>

An overview and a screenshot of the webpage are provided below.

Shaping electron wavepackets with light; Shaping light with electron wavepackets

The fourth Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar touches upon the following topics:

- Electron and photon beam shaping
- Electron-light interaction
- Light-electron interaction with shaped beam
- Coherent Bremsstrahlung, Cherenkov and transition radiation
- Plasmon and PINEM (photon-induced near-field electron microscopy)
- Smith-Purcell radiation.

Recent years have seen growing interest in the shaping of the wavefunction of photons and electrons.

For example, it is possible to produce waves with the characteristic helical wavefront of vortex beams or with other interesting shapes, or in the shape of a [Bessel beam](#) in order to test the properties of the [Cherenkov radiation](#). The latter is the characteristic light that charged particles emit when they travel through dielectric media close to the speed of light, generating a phenomenon that is the light equivalent of a sonic boom).

The talk explores how such new capabilities could enable scientists to exploit new kinds of interactions between light and matter.

It also discusses how shaping the electron wavefunction can alter fundamental processes of light emission. By exploiting the exactly-periodic and highly stable nature of electron wave interference in electron microscopes, it is possible to control the frequency and angular spectrum of the emitted light.

Conversely, shaping wave-packets of light allows one to alter the electron wavefunction with a very high efficiency (i.e. altering completely the shape of the electron beam). This can be done, for example, by means of surface plasmon excitations.

Different examples are made of shaping the spatial/temporal profile of laser pulses. This way one can produce electron vortex beams and control their acceleration.

The shaping of the electron wavefunction is also shown applied to many different emission mechanisms - for example the Bremsstrahlung, Cherenkov and transition radiation. WIn these cases the coherent shape of the electron beam translates to desirable and/or unexpected properties of the resulting X-ray or visible radiation.

A new era of wave shape manipulation is therefore predicted.

This talk is geared towards an audience of physicists interested in the unconventional possibilities coming from beam-shaping implementations realised outside the field of electron microscopy.

It also provides an overview of some common misunderstandings and imprecisions in the calculation of electron-light-matter interaction, and available strategies for tackling them in a correct manner.

About the speaker

Ido Kaminer is a faculty member at the Technion Faculty of Electrical Engineering. He studies the fundamentals of light-matter interactions in nanophotonics and in settings of 2D materials, developing new concepts for light generation in spectral ranges inaccessible by existing technology. Ido's research specifically focuses on the light-matter interactions of shaped particle wavefunctions, in which he made contributions to the quantum electrodynamics of relativistic electron wavefunctions. Ido is an Azrieli Faculty Fellow and won a Rothschild Fellowship, MIT-Technion Scholarship, and a Marie Curie Fellowship, for his

postdoc. During his PhD, Ido has discovered new classes of accelerating beams in nonlinear optics and electromagnetism, for which he received the 2012 Israel Physical Society Prize, and the 2014 APS Award for Outstanding Doctoral Dissertation in Laser Science.

Figure 2 - Screenshot of the fourth interdisciplinary training webinar page on the Q-SORT website

4 CONCLUSIONS

This is the fourth Interdisciplinary Training Webinar produced for Q-SORT by [QED](#), with additional support from partner [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#).

In the past few years we have seen a consistent rise in the popularity and value of webinars as an essential training, communication, and engagement tool.

The video of the webinar also offers a unique opportunity for engagement. The project will continue to promote on-demand webinars so that their audiences will get larger and more engaged, and spend more time watching webinars, both live and on-demand. In planning the next webinars we will evaluate the effectiveness of the previous ones and use it as a guideline to help the Q-SORT consortium create, promote, and deliver even more successful webinars.

ANNEX 1: SHAPING ELECTRON WAVEPACKETS WITH LIGHT; SHAPING LIGHT WITH ELECTRON WAVEPACKETS

Shaping electron wavepackets with light

Technion
Israel Institute of Technology

Shaping light with electron wavepackets

Ido Kaminer

Newly established group at the Technion

- Setting a new Ultrafast Transmission Electron Microscope
- Combined theory and experiments
- Research opportunities for excellent graduate students and postdocs

with
John D. Joannopoulos
and **Marin Soljačić**

with
Fabrizio Carbone

Motivation

The composite image illustrates the motivation for X-ray technology through several components:

- Diffraction Diagram:** Shows a series of wavefronts from a source labeled 'TX' passing through a series of slits. A detector or screen is labeled 'C', and the angle of diffraction is labeled θ .
- X-ray Tube Schematic:** A cross-sectional diagram of an X-ray tube. It features a 'Tungsten Anode' at the front and a 'Cathode' at the back. An 'Electron Beam' is shown originating from the cathode and striking the anode. This interaction produces an 'X-Ray Beam' that is emitted from the anode. The tube is divided into an 'Anode Arm' and a 'Cathode Arm'.
- Medical Application:** A photograph of a medical professional in a white coat and mask using an X-ray machine to examine a patient lying on a table.
- Historical Apparatus:** A detailed illustration of Röntgen's experimental apparatus from 1895. It includes a Ruhmkorff induction coil (labeled 'B'), a photographic plate (labeled 'C'), and a Hittorf-Crookes evacuated tube (labeled 'T').
- Portrait and Medal:** A portrait of Wilhelm C. Röntgen and a gold medal awarded to him.

Fig. 1.1. Röntgen's experimental apparatus in 1895: B, Ruhmkorff induction coil; C, photographic plate; T, Hittorf-Crookes evacuated tube.

Wilhelm C. Röntgen

Rough outline

Phased-array antennas in x-rays?

- Why it sounds easy to do with electron **beam shaping**
- Why it's not easy
- What fundamental scientific question is hiding there
- What is the meaning of the *quantum wavefunction*?
- Bigger picture
- But first – what do I mean by electron **beam shaping**

Beam shaping?

Wave interference
↓
Structuring wave patterns
↓
Control of **interactions**:

Shaping light

STED: Nobel Prize in Chemistry 2014 (Stefan Hell)

(stimulated emission depletion microscopy)

Shape the interaction with atoms?

Light beam carrying orbital angular momentum (OAM)

- A. M. Yao and M. J. Padgett, "Orbital angular momentum: origins, behavior and applications," *Advances in Optics and Photonics*, 3, 161 (2011).
- A. Picon, A. Benseny, J. Mompart, J. R. Vazquez de Aldana, L. Plaja, G. F. Calvo, and L. Roso, "Transferring orbital and spin angular momenta of light to atoms," *New Journal of Physics*, 12, 083053 (2010).
- A. Picon, J. Mompart, J. R. V. de Aldana, L. Plaja, G. F. Calvo, and L. Roso, "Photoionization with orbital angular momentum beams," *Optics express*, 18, 3660-71 (2010).
- A. Afanasev, C. E. Carlson, and A. Mukherjee, "Off-axis excitation of hydrogenlike atoms by twisted photons," *Physical Review A*, 88, 033841 (2013).
- A. Afanasev, C. E. Carlson, and A. Mukherjee, "Highmultipole excitations of hydrogen-like atoms by twisted photons near a phase singularity," *Journal of Optics*, 18, 7, 074013 (2016).

Vortex Electron Beams

- Prediction Bliokh et al
 - Bliokh, Bliokh, Savel'ev, Nori, **PRL** 99, 190404 (2007)
- Observation by Tonomura
 - Uchida&Tonomura, **Nature** 464, 737 (2010)
- Other groups fabricated thin masks and other methods to imbue electrons with OAM
 - Verbeeck et al., **Nature** 467, 301 (2010)
 - McMorran et al., **Science** 331, 192 (2011)
- The actual cylindrical (Bessel) beam was created experimentally
 - Grillo *et al.*, **PRX** 4, 011013 (2014).

H. Larocque, I. Kaminer, V. Grillo, G. Leuchs, M. J. Padgett, R. W. Boyd, M. Segev, and E. Karimi, "Twisted" Electrons, **Contemporary of Physics** (2017)

The simplest electron “shaping”

Tomomura, Akira, et al. "Demonstration of single-electron buildup of an interference pattern." Am. J. Phys 57.2 (1989): 117-120.

Fig. 3. Electron-optical diagram of the interference experiment.

Motivation

Wilhelm C. Röntgen

Fig. 1.1. Röntgen's experimental apparatus in 1895: B, Ruhmkorff induction coil; C, photographic plate; T, Hittorf-Crookes evacuated tube.

Motivation

electron interference = "antenna arrays"
of sub-nm periodicity

Shaping electrons to make bremsstrahlung directional and monochromatic

electron interference = "antenna arrays"
of **sub-nm periodicity**

<http://coen.boisestate.edu/corrosionlab/education/lego-mse-lab/tem/>

Shaping electrons to make bremsstrahlung directional and monochromatic

Murdia*, Rivera*, Wong, Joannopoulos, Soljačić, Kaminer, "Controlling Radiation by Shaping Electron Wavefunctions" (arXiv: 1712.04529)

What is the meaning of the Schrödinger wavefunction?

semi-classical: $\rho(\mathbf{r}, t) = \psi^*(\mathbf{r}, t)\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$

$J := \langle J \rangle = \langle \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) | J | \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \rangle$
 "the semi-classical approach"

$$J = \frac{1}{2m} \left\{ \psi^* \left(\frac{\hbar}{i} \nabla - q\mathbf{A} \right) \psi + \psi \left(\frac{\hbar}{i} \nabla - q\mathbf{A} \right)^* \psi^* \right\}$$

$$J = \frac{\hbar}{2mi} \{ \psi^* \nabla \psi - \psi \nabla \psi^* \}$$

$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho_f$
$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$
$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t}$
$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{J}_f + \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t}$

This is how our intuition works, and often how we teach quantum mechanics

But it is simply incorrect.
 Still it is widely used,
 and sometimes it even works **(?!?)**

"It is noted that semi-classical analysis of spontaneous emission is not consistent with conventional QED theory"
 Pan, Gover, arXiv:1804.00053 (2018)

Schrödinger, Born, and Feynman

What is the meaning of $\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$?

$$\rho(\mathbf{r}, t) = \psi^*(\mathbf{r}, t)\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$$

$$\mathbf{J} = \frac{1}{2m} \left\{ \psi^* \left(\frac{\hbar}{i} \nabla - q\mathbf{A} \right) \psi + \psi \left(\frac{\hbar}{i} \nabla - q\mathbf{A} \right)^* \psi^* \right\}$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}$$

$$\mathbf{J} = \frac{\hbar}{2mi} \{ \psi^* \nabla \psi - \psi \nabla \psi^* \}$$

When Schrödinger first discovered his equation he discovered the conservation law of Eq. (21.8) as a consequence of his equation. But he imagined incorrectly that ρ was the electric charge density of the electron and that \mathbf{J} was the electric current density, so he thought that the electrons interacted with the electromagnetic field through these charges and currents.

When he solved his equations for the hydrogen atom and calculated ψ , ... there were currents moving around...

He soon found on doing a number of problems that it didn't work out quite right.

It was at this point that Born made an essential contribution to our ideas regarding quantum mechanics. It was Born who correctly (as far as we know) interpreted the ψ of the Schrödinger equation in terms of a probability amplitude—that very difficult idea that the square of the amplitude is not the charge density but is only the probability per unit volume of finding an electron there, and that when you do find the electron some place the entire charge is there. That whole idea is due to Born.

The wave function ψ for an electron in an atom does not, then, describe a smeared-out electron with a smooth charge density. The electron is either here, or there, or somewhere else, but wherever it is, it is a point charge.

As we'll see pretty soon, this is not the entire story either!

All quoted from Feynman Lectures III_21

Also online in

www.feynmanlectures.caltech.edu/III_21.html

Examples why the semi-classical description is wrong

optical medium

optical medium

Cherenkov radiation through a QED formalism:
 for shaped electron wavepackets
 Kaminer et al., **PRX** 6, 011006 (2016)

“Radiation from a wide quantum electron” *in preparation*
 R. Remez, A. Karnieli, S. Trajtenberg-Mills, N. Shapira,
 I. Kaminer, Y. Lereah, and A. Arie

Narrow (classical) electron

Classical approach

Wide electron

ψ

Semi-classical continuous charge approach

Wide electron

ψ

Semi-classical probability approach

So all is incoherent?

Who cares about it beyond
 electron microscopists?

Cherenkov radiation through a QED formalism:
 for shaped electron wavepackets
 Kaminer et al., **PRX** 6, 011006 (2016)

Radiation from electrons
 carrying OAM?

$$|p_1\rangle \rightarrow \text{cloud} \rightarrow \sigma_1 \propto |S_1|^2$$

$$|p_1\rangle + |p_2\rangle \rightarrow \text{cloud} \rightarrow |S_1|^2 + |S_2|^2$$

No dependence on the relative phase! ?

$$M_{p_i^{cyl} \rightarrow p_f^{cyl} + k^{cyl}}^{density}(t, r, \varphi, z) = \left\langle p_f^{cyl} \text{ particle}, k^{cyl} \text{ photon} \left| \underbrace{\psi^\dagger \gamma^0 \gamma^\mu \psi}_{\hat{=} j^\mu(t, r, \varphi, z)} q A_\mu(t, r, \varphi, z) \right| p_i^{cyl} \text{ particle}, 0 \right\rangle$$

$$\int_0^\infty J_{l_i}(p_{ir}r/\hbar) J_{l_f}(p_{fr}r/\hbar) J_{l_{ph}=l_i-l_f}(k_r r) r dr = \frac{\cos(l_i \alpha_f - l_f \alpha_i)}{2\pi S_\Delta(\frac{1}{\hbar} p_{ir}, \frac{1}{\hbar} p_{fr}, k_r)}$$

Gervois&Navelet, *J. Math. Phys.* 25, 3350 (1984)

The Čerenkov angle splits in two!

- $\theta_{ph} = \theta_i - \theta_{cR}$
- $\theta_{ph} = \theta_{cR} - \theta_i$
- $\theta_{ph} = \theta_i + \theta_{cR}$

Preferred emission angles controlled by OAM, spin, and polarization

Creates coupling between the charged particle and the emitted photon

Kaminer et al., *PRX* 6, 011006 (2016)

$\theta_i = 0.1^\circ$

$\beta = 0.685$

$n = 1.45986$

$l_{ph} = 8$

So all is incoherent? Consequence for high energy physics?

Just philosophy?

Cherenkov radiation through a QED formalism:
 for shaped electron wavepackets
 Kaminer et al., **PRX** 6, 011006 (2016)

Who cares about it beyond
 electron microscopists?

$$|p_1\rangle \rightarrow \text{cloud} \rightarrow \sigma_1 \propto |S_1|^2$$

$$|p_1\rangle + |p_2\rangle \rightarrow \text{cloud} \rightarrow |S_1|^2 + |S_2|^2$$

No dependence on the relative phase!?

Consequence for high energy physics

H. Larocque, I. Kaminer,
V. Grillo, R. W Boyd, E. Karimi,
“Twisting neutrons may reveal
their internal structure”,
Nature Phys. 14, 1-2 (2018).
(Correspondence)

Schrödinger, Born, and Feynman

a Incident wave function Ψ_{IL}

b Plasmon electric potential ϕ_m

c Product of incident wavefunction and potential $\Psi_{IL} \cdot \phi_m$

d Wavefunction in the detector plane $\mathcal{F}(\Psi_{IL} \cdot \phi_m)$

Detector

Cherenkov radiation through a QED formalism:
 for shaped electron wavepackets
 Kaminer et al., **PRX** 6, 011006 (2016)

... the conservation law of Eq. (21.8) as the consequence of his equation. The electron and the current density, so he thought the ... quite right

... regarding quantum mechanics was Born who correctly terms of a probability amplitude. That very difficult idea that probability per unit volume of finding an electron there, and e. That whole idea is due to Born.

... n, describe a smeared-out electron with a smooth where else, but wherever it is, **it is a point charge.**

???

Well... it depends what you measure

“Probing the symmetry of the potential of localized surface plasmon resonances with phase-shaped electron beams”

Guzzinati, Béch, Lourenco-Martins, Martin, Kociak, and Verbeeck,

Nature Communications, 8, 14999 (2017)

So... phased-array antennas in x-rays?

electron interference = "antenna arrays"
of sub-angstrom periodicity

Fig. 3. Electron-optical diagram of the interference experiment.

The full QED formalism and a toy example

bremsstrahlung from a shaped electron:

incident superposition electron

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{|p_1\rangle + e^{i\xi}|p_2\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$E_i = 200 \text{ keV}$

single beam

$\omega = 10 \text{ keV}$

$\omega = 100 \text{ keV}$

Nick Rivera Chitraang Murdia

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dk} = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^5} \frac{\omega_k \beta_{p'} E_{p'}}{8 \beta_p E_p} \int d\Omega_{p'} \times \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{s,s',\epsilon(k)} |\mathcal{M}(p_1 \rightarrow p'k) + e^{i\xi} \mathcal{M}(p_2 \rightarrow p'k)|^2 \right)$$

$\frac{d\sigma}{dk}$
($10^{-8} \text{ b sr}^{-1} \text{ eV}^{-1}$)

Murdia*, Rivera*, Wong, Joannopoulos, Soljačić, Kaminer, "Controlling Radiation by Shaping Electron Wavefunctions" (arXiv: 1712.04529)

The critical issue is always whether the cross-term vanishes or contributes

Mid-summary

- Shaping electron wavepackets can alter light-matter interactions in unexpected ways
- What is the absolute limit for electron radiation given optimal electron wave shaping?

- Electrons in atoms have orbitals with certain values of OAM – let's shape light to match its OAM
- Can we shape light on the atomic scale to gain new control over light-matter interactions?

The electron is **not just a point charge** – its OAM matters

Macroscopic QED formalism

$$A_i(\mathbf{r}) = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{\pi\epsilon_0}} \int d\omega' \frac{\omega'}{c^2} \int d\mathbf{r}' \sqrt{\text{Im } \epsilon(\mathbf{r}', \omega')} \mathbf{G}_{ij}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'; \omega') \hat{f}_j(\mathbf{r}', \omega') + \text{H.c.}$$

$$B_i(\mathbf{r}) = (\nabla \times \mathbf{A})_i = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{\pi\epsilon_0}} \int d\omega' \frac{\omega'}{c^2} \int d\mathbf{r}' \sqrt{\text{Im } \epsilon(\mathbf{r}', \omega')} \epsilon_{ilm} \partial_l G_{mj}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'; \omega') \hat{f}_j(\mathbf{r}', \omega') + \text{H.c.}$$

Second quantization of light dressed by the medium

Fermi's Golden Rule

Electronic transition in an atom:

The electron OAM is here

$$\frac{2\pi}{\hbar^2} \frac{e^2 \hbar}{\pi\epsilon_0 m_e^2 c^2} \int d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \psi_e^*(\mathbf{r}) \psi_e(\mathbf{r}') (\text{Im } G_{ij}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', \omega_0)) (p_i \psi_g(\mathbf{r})) (p_j^* \psi_g^*(\mathbf{r}'))$$

$$\Gamma = \frac{4\alpha\omega_0}{m_e^2 c^2 (\epsilon_r + 1)} \eta_0^3 \int d\theta du u^2 e^{-2\eta_0 k z_0 u} |\langle g | (\hat{\epsilon}(\mathbf{q}) \cdot \mathbf{p}) e^{i\mathbf{q} \cdot \boldsymbol{\rho} - q(z-z_0)} | e \rangle|^2 \left(\frac{1}{\pi} \frac{\frac{\sigma_R u}{\sigma_I}}{(\frac{\sigma_R u}{\sigma_I})^2 + (1-u)^2} \right)$$

exponential dependence in the distance
matrix element with a plasmon field
delta function in the lossless limit

Rivera*, Kaminer*, Zhen, Joannopoulos, Soljacic (*Science* 353, 263 (2016))

Machado*, Rivera*, Buljan,
Soljagic, Kaminer,
"Shaping Polaritons to Reshape
Selection Rules"
(arXiv:1610.01668) *under review*

Francisco Machado

Machado*, Rivera*, Buljan,
 Soljagic, Kaminer,
 "Shaping Polaritons to Reshape
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 (arXiv:1610.01668) under review

Francisco Machado

Vortex plasmons and their OAM

Spektor et al. (Giessen, Orenstein, Aeschlimann) **Science** 355, 1187 (2017)

Spektor, David, Gjonaj, Bartal, Orenstein, **Nano Letters** 15, 5739 (2015).

The ultrafast transmission electron microscope (UEM)

The UEM is a great opportunity to probe fundamental questions of light-matter interactions

The ultrafast transmission electron microscope (UEM)

The Technion new UEM (end of 2018)

- JEOL 2100Plus Thermionic (40kV - 200kV)
- STEM, HAADF
- EELS (GATAN GIF)
- Light Conversion 40W Carbide
- Pump pulses tunable (visible - far IR)
- Both 0 and 90 degrees pump coupling

J. Mater. Res. 2017, 32, 239-247

UEM advantages vs competing approaches:

- Electron probe goes **through** the material
- **Electron diffraction by light waves**

Evidence for electron diffraction by light in the UEM

Fabrizio Carbone's group

Vanacore et al., look for it in Nature Comm. (2018)

PINEM

Photon-Induced Nearfield Electron Microscopy

Barwick, Flannigan, Zewail, *Nature*, 462, 902 (2009)

quantum

Quantum walk - PINEM

Feist, A., Echtenkamp, K.E., Schauss, J., Yalunin, S.V., Schäfer, S. and Ropers, C.,
“Quantum coherent optical phase modulation in an ultrafast transmission electron microscope”
Nature 521, 200 (2015).

Shaped electron pulses – pulse trains

Morimoto, Y. and Baum, P., "Diffraction and microscopy with attosecond electron pulse trains". **Nature Physics** 14, 252 (2018)

Priebe, K.E., Rathje, C., Yalunin, S.V., Hohage, T., Feist, A., Schäfer, S. and Ropers, C., "Attosecond electron pulse trains and quantum state reconstruction in ultrafast transmission electron microscopy". **Nature Photonics** 11, 793 (2017)

Also: Kozal et al., Hommelhoff group, **PRL** 120, 103203 (2018)

What we would like to find

- A single electron shaped as a train of pulses – will it emit like a bunched electron beam?
- Can we improve FELs by bunching electron pulses on the single-electron level?
- Maybe there are opportunities for new kinds of radiation sources hiding here?
- What is the fundamental bound for acceleration gradients given a full control of the wavepacket?

The theory behind PINEM

Ori Reinhardt

(also by Sang Tae Park
 in unpublished work)

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m\gamma} \nabla^2 \psi = 0 \quad \left(\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \psi - \nabla^2 \psi + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \psi = 0 \right)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + i \frac{e}{\hbar} \phi \quad \nabla \rightarrow \nabla + i \frac{e}{\hbar} \mathbf{A}$$

After the paraxial-electron approximation

$$i\hbar \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) \tilde{\psi} + \frac{\hbar^2}{2\gamma m} \nabla^2 \tilde{\psi} + \text{Re} \left\{ \frac{iev}{\omega} e^{-i\omega t} E_z \right\} \tilde{\psi} = 0$$

García de Abajo, Asenjo-García,
 Kociak, **Nano Lett.** 10, 1859 (2010)

Park, Lin, Zewail, **NJP**
 12, 123028 (2010)

$$\tilde{\psi}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \psi_0(\mathbf{r} - vt\hat{z}) \sum_l \text{(envelope)} \text{(Fourier series)} e^{il\omega \left(\frac{z}{v} - t \right)} f_l(\mathbf{r})$$

$$f_l = \left(\frac{-g}{|g|} \right)^l J_l(|g|)$$

“The PINEM field”

$$g(x, y, z) = \frac{e}{\hbar\omega} \int_{-\infty}^z dz' E_z(x, y, z') e^{-i\omega z'/v}$$

Probability of $l\hbar\omega$ energy change $P_l = J_l^2(|g|)$

The theory behind PINEM

Ori Reinhardt

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m\gamma} \nabla^2 \psi = 0 \quad \left(\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \psi - \nabla^2 \psi + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \psi = 0 \right)$$

After the paraxial-electron approximation

“Optical interaction of a free electron with a frequency comb”
 Reinhardt and Kaminer, *submitted*
 “Bloch oscillations of a free electron in a strong field”,
 Pick*, Reinhardt*, Plotnik, Wong, Kaminer, *CLEO 2018*

García de Abajo, Asenjo-García,
 Kociak, *Nano Lett.* 10, 1859 (2010)

Park, Lin, Zewail, *NJP*
 12, 123028 (2010)

Gover and Pan, *Phys. Lett. A* 382, 1550 (2018)
 Pan and Gover, *arXiv:1805.08210* (2018)

$$\tilde{\psi}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \psi_0(\mathbf{r} - vt\hat{z}) \sum_l e^{il\omega(\frac{z}{v}-t)} f_l(\mathbf{r})$$

“The PINEM field”

$$g(x, y, z) = \frac{e}{\hbar\omega} \int_{-\infty}^z dz' E_z(x, y, z') e^{-i\omega z'/v}$$

Probability of $l\hbar\omega$ energy change $P_l = J_l^2(|g|)$

So... how do we describe the electron interaction here?

- The field is treated classically
- The interaction is wavepacket-dependent
- Treated semi-classically $J := \langle \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) | J | \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \rangle$
- At least for now...

High harmonic plasmon generation

Grazing-angle interaction of electron beam with a plasmonic surface
(The electron is driven by light)

Ultrafast plasmon pulses with fs pulse duration at nm length scales

“Ultrafast multi-harmonic plasmon generation by optically dressed electrons”,
Rivera, Wong, Soljacic, and Kaminer, *submitted*

High harmonic plasmon generation

Required driving field is 3-5 orders of magnitude lower than in conventional HHG

“Ultrafast multi-harmonic plasmon generation by optically dressed electrons”,
 Rivera, Wong, Soljagic, and Kaminer, *submitted*

Remaining challenges

- What will be the role of the wavepacket in all of these processes?
- Can we pre-shape the electron prior to the interaction to have it alter the interaction down the road?
- Improve radiation sources?
- What are the limits to electron acceleration given a pre-shaped electron wavepacket?

There are still important unsolved *classical* questions

- Detectors

Artificial photonic materials for particle identification
e.g., pion-kaon separation

Fast follow up + preliminary measurements CERN LHCb

First Cherenkov ring detected from a photonic crystal

X. Lin et al., *Nature Physics*, advanced online publication (2018)

- Limits

What is the *maximum* possible radiation emission or energy loss/gain of a charged particle in an arbitrary optical medium

Y. Yang et al., *Nature Physics*, accepted (2018)

Kaminer et al., **PRX**
 6, 011006 (2016)

Rivera*, Kaminer*, Zhen, Joannopoulos,
 Soljagic, **Science** 353, 263 (2016)

Machado*, Rivera*,
 Buljan, Soljagic, Kaminer,
 (arXiv:1610.01668)

Newly established group at the Technion

- Setting a new Ultrafast Transmission Electron Microscope
- Combined theory and experiments
- Research opportunities for excellent graduate students and postdocs

Vanacore et al., look for it
 in **Nature Comm.** (2018)

21 22

Murdia*, Rivera*, Wong, Joannopoulos, Soljacić, Kaminer,
 "Controlling Radiation by Shaping Electron Wavefunctions" (arXiv: 1712.04529)

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL